

Fluorine Containing Bioactive Heterocycles : Part I. Synthesis and Antibacterial, Fungicidal and Antiviral Activities of Some New Fluorine Containing 3-Dialkylaminoethylthio-5-Morpholinomethyl[1,2,4]Triazino[5,6-b]Indoles and 3-[2-(5-Benzylidene-4-Thiazolidinone)Diazo]Indol-2-Ones

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A series of new fluorine containing 3-dialkyl-aminoethylthio-5-morpholinomethyl [1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indoles and 3-[2-(5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone)diazo]indol-2-ones have been synthesized; the former by the reaction of different dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride with fluorinated 5-morpholinomethyl[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thiones in presence of sodium hydroxide and the latter, by treating fluorinated isatin-3-thiosemicarbazones, chloroacetic acid and sodium acetate with different aryl aldehydes in glacial acetic acid. All the synthesized compounds have been characterized by their spectral and elemental analysis. All the compounds have been screened for their antibacterial activity against gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus albus* and gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*. A representative number of compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria burnsii* and also for their antiviral activities.

THE indole nucleus is well known for its pharmaceutical and biochemical activities^{1,2}. Indole-2,3-dione, an important indole derivative, is found to possess antiviral³, antifungal⁴ and antibacterial⁵ activity. 5-Bromoisatin has shown analgesic activity stronger than that of aspirin⁶. Various triazino[5,6-b]indoles have been synthesized and most of them have shown antiviral and antibacterial activities⁷. Isatin- β -thiosemicarbazones are well known antiviral agents against rabbitpox, cowpox, alastrin and various viruses^{8,9}. Indolylthiazolidinones have also been found to possess antiviral and antimicrobial activities^{10,11}. These observations prompted us to undertake the synthesis of fluorine containing 3-dialkylaminoethylthio-5-morpholinomethyl[1,2,4]-triazino[5,6-b]indoles and 3-[2-(5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone)diazo]indol-2-ones [Scheme-I].

Experimental

Melting points of all synthesized compounds are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (model-337) in KBr Pellets. PMR spectra were recorded in trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) on Perkin-Elmer (model-RB-12; 60 MHz). TMS was taken as an internal standard.

5/6-Fluoroindole-2,3-diones(I) :

These compounds were synthesized according to the method of Yen¹² and Sadler¹³ from 4-fluoroaniline and 3-fluoroaniline respectively. 5-Fluoroindole-2,3-dione, yield 62%, m.p. 221-2° (Lit.¹² m.p.

Where: X = 5-F, 6-F [VI], 7-F, 8-F [IV].

- NR₂ = Morpholino, Piperidino.

Pyrrolidino, Diethylamino.

- Ar' = 4-Fluorophenyl, Phenyl,

4-Chlorophenyl, 2-Furyl, 4-Nitrophenyl, Dimethylaminophenyl.

SCHEME-I

223°); 6-Fluoroindole-2,3-dione, yield 64%, m.p. 195-6° (Lit.¹⁸ m.p. 197).

5/6-Fluoro-1-morpholinomethylindole-2,3-diones(II) :

The compounds were synthesized according to the method of Wyeth¹⁴. A mixture of required 5/6-fluoroindole-2,3-dione (0.01 M), morpholine (0.012 M) and formaldehyde (0.015 M) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 40 minutes. On cooling the reaction mixture, crystals separated out which were recrystallized from ethanol. 5-Fluoro-1-morpholinomethyl-indole-2,3-dione, yield 73%, m.p. 150 (Found : N 10.51 calculated for C₁₃H₁₃FN₂O₃, N, 10.60%); 6-Fluoro-1-morpholinomethylindole-2,3-dione, yield 68%, m.p. 155° (Found : N 10.42 calculated for C₁₃H₁₃FN₂O₃, N, 10.60%).

7/8-Fluoro-5-morpholinomethyl-[1,2,4]-triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thiones(III) :

A mixture of appropriate 1-morpholinomethyl-indole-2,3-dione (0.01 M) and thiosemicarbazide (0.011 M) was refluxed with potassium carbonate (0.015 M) in water for 5-6 hours¹⁵. The solution was filtered, cooled and acidified to give corresponding 5-morpholinomethyl[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thione, which was purified by recrystallization from DMF and gave single spot in TLC in various solvent systems.

7-Fluoro-5-morpholinomethyl-[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thione, yield 61% m.p. >300° (Found : N 21.78 calculated for C₁₄H₁₄N₅FOS, N, 21.94%); 8-Fluoro-5-morpholinomethyl[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thione, yield 64%, m.p. >300° (Found : N 21.71 calculated for C₁₄H₁₄N₅FOS, N, 21.94%).

3-Dialkylaminoethylthio-7/8-fluoro-5-morpholinomethyl[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indoles(IV) :

These derivatives were synthesized according to the method of Gladych *et al*¹⁶. The aqueous solution of dialkylaminoethylchloride hydrochloride (0.015 M) was added to a stirred mixture of appropriate fluorinated 5-morpholinomethyl-[1,2,4] triazino [5,6-b] indole-3-thione (0.01 M) in N sodium hydroxide (10 ml). The mixture was diluted, acidified, filtered and the filtrate was made alkaline to give the desired compound. All synthesized compounds gave single spots in T. L. C. Their analytical data and antibacterial activity are given in Table 1.

5/6-Fluoroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazones(V) :

A mixture of 5/6-fluoroindole-2,3-dione (0.01 M) and thiosemicarbazide (0.01 M) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 40 minutes. On cooling the reaction mixture, crystals separated out which were filtered and recrystallized from ethanol.

5-Fluoroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone, yield 94%, m.p. 275-6°; 6-Fluoroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone, yield 97%, m.p. 240-1°.

3-[2-(5-Benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone) diazo]-5/6-fluoroindol-2-ones(VI) :

A mixture of 5/6-fluoroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mole), chloroacetic acid (0.015 mole) and sodium acetate (0.01 mole) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (20-30 ml) for half an hour. An appropriate aryl aldehydes (0.01 mole) was then added and the mixture further refluxed for 4-5 hours¹⁰, cooled and filtered. Analytical data and antibacterial activity of compounds prepared are given in Table 2.

Evaluation of biological activity :

The antibacterial activity of all synthesized compounds was studied¹⁷ against gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus albus* and gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* in different concentrations ranging from 4 µg/ml-20 µg/ml. Antibacterial activity at two particular concentrations, 16 µg/ml and 20 µg/ml, is being given in Tables 1 and 2.

The fungicidal activity of compounds of type VI was studied against *Alternaria burnsii* according to method¹⁸. The test fungus was grown on Potato Dextrose Agar medium, in which desired amount of fungicide was previously incorporated in 500 ppm and 1000 ppm concentration; control consisted of plane PDA plates inoculated with pathogen. The linear growth at 25° was measured after 7 days.

The antiviral activity of some of the compounds (Nos. 1, 8 of Table 1 and Nos. 1, 8 of Table 2) was studied against *Semliki forest* virus. 2 mg quantity of each of the compounds was given to test mouse (20 gram) in two divided doses (1 mg each injection) at 24 and 48 hours after virus challenge (100 LD 50).

Results and Discussion .

Spectral Studies (IR & PMR) :

Indole-2,3-diones I, show strong absorption bands in the region of 3300-3500 cm⁻¹ (>N-H stretching) and strong >C=O absorption in the range of 1735-1730 cm⁻¹. When compounds I were subjected to Mannich reaction, yielding compounds II, new resonance signals appeared due to -N.CH₂-N- protons at δ 4.35 ppm. Further, >NH absorption band disappeared providing a strong support for formation of N-Mannich bases. Compounds II when treated with thiosemicarbazide and potassium carbonate gave III, and the structure of latter confirmed by disappearances of >CO absorption bands (1735-1730 cm⁻¹) and appearance of new -C=N absorption band between 1630-1600 cm⁻¹. Compounds III, on treatment with

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF FLUORINE CONTAINING 3-DIALKYLAMINOETHYLTHIO-5-MORPHOLINOMETHYL[1,2,4]TRIAZINO[5,6-b]INDOLES IV :

Sl. No.	X Substituent in Ar	-NR ₂	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N% analysis		Antibacterial activity			
						Calcd.	Found	<i>S. albus</i>		<i>E. coli</i>	
								16 µg/ml	20 µg/ml	16 µg/ml	20 µg/ml
1.	8-F	Diethylamino-	286	71	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N ₆ FOS	20.09	19.85	++	++	+	++
2.	8-F	Piperidino-	212	62	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₆ FOS	19.53	20.22	+	++	+	++
3.	8-F	Pyrrolidino-	201	71	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₆ FOS	20.19	20.01	±	±	+	+
4.	8-F	morpholino-	221	66	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₆ FO ₂ S	19.44	19.60	±	±	+	++
5.	7-F	Diethylamino-	228	69	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N ₆ FOS	20.09	20.25	+	++	++	+++
6.	7-F	Piperidino-	232	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₆ FOS	19.53	19.15	+	++	+	++
7.	7-F	Pyrrolidino-	>300	70	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₆ FOS	20.19	20.30	±	±	±	+
8.	7-F	morpholino-	229	68	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₆ FO ₂ S	19.44	19.41	+	+	+	+

- Insensitive.
 ± 0.1 to 0.3 cm area of inhibition of bacterial zone.
 + 0.3 to 0.5 cm " " " "
 ++ 0.5 to 0.7 cm " " " "
 +++ 0.7 to 0.9 cm " " " "

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF FLUORINE CONTAINING 3-[2-(5-BENZYLIDENE-4-THIAZOLIDINONE)DIAZO]INDOL-2-ONES VI :

Sl. No.	X Substituent in Ar	Ar'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N% analysis		Antibacterial activity			
						Calcd.	Found	<i>S. albus</i>		<i>E. coli</i>	
								16 µg/ml	20 µg/ml	16 µg/ml	20 µg/ml
1.	6-F	Phenyl	272-4	69	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₄ FO ₂ S	15.30	15.12	±	±	+	+
2.	5-F	Phenyl	>300	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₄ FO ₂ S	15.30	15.21	±	±	±	+
3.	6-F	4-F Phenyl-	>300	95	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ F ₂ O ₂ S	14.58	14.39	+	++	++	+++
4.	5-F	4-F Phenyl-	247 (decomp.)	85	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ F ₂ O ₂ S	14.58	14.41	+	++	++	++
5.	5-F	Dimethylaminophenyl-	255	81	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₆ FO ₂ S	17.11	17.01	±	±	±	+
6.	6-F	Dimethylaminophenyl-	242	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₆ FO ₂ S	17.11	16.98	±	±	+	++
7.	5-F	4-Cl Phenyl-	>300	77	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ FCIS	13.98	13.89	+	+	+	++
8.	6-F	4-Cl Phenyl-	>300	91	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ FCIS	13.98	13.82	±	±	+	++
9.	5-F	2-furyl-	276	82	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₄ FO ₂ S	15.73	15.68	±	±	+	+
10.	6-F	2-furyl-	>300	83	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₄ FO ₂ S	15.73	15.52	±	±	+	+
11.	5-F	4-NO ₂ phenyl-	>300	87	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ FO ₄ S	17.03	17.00	++	+++	+++	+++
12.	6-F	4-NO ₂ phenyl-	325-6	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ FO ₄ S	17.03	16.98	++	+++	++	+++

- Insensitive.
 ± 0.1 to 0.3 cm area of inhibition of bacterial zone.
 + 0.3 to 0.5 cm " " " "
 ++ 0.5 to 0.7 cm " " " "
 +++ 0.7 to 0.9 cm " " " "

dialkylaminoethylchloride hydrochloride gave IV, the PMR spectra of which show resonance signals between δ 3.5 to 4.2 ppm (broad due to -SCH₂CH₂-N protons and N-CH₂ protons and aromatic protons signal in the range of δ 7.0-8.0 ppm. Compounds IV, show absorption bands at 1630-1600 cm⁻¹ (-C=N stretching).

Compounds I, on treatment with thiosemicarbazide gave V, which show three different >NH absorptions between 3500-3300 cm⁻¹ and >C=O absorption bands in the range of 1735-1730 cm⁻¹. Compound V, when cyclized with chloroacetic acid, gave compounds VI which show broad absorption bands due to >NH stretching between 3500-3300 cm⁻¹.

In all the above compounds, the absorption bands due to Ar. C-F appears between 1260-1200 cm⁻¹.

Biological Activity :

The antibacterial activity of the compounds indicated that all compounds are effective against gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*. Compounds having -NO₂ group were found to be more powerful antibacterial agents as compared to other analogs (Table 2).

The fungicidal activity of 3-[2-(5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone)diazo]indol-2-ones has been given

TABLE 3—FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF FLUORINE CONTAINING 3-[2-(5-BENZYLIDENE-4-THIAZOLIDINONE) DIAZO]-INDOL-2-ONES IV : [AGAINST "ALTERNARIA BURNSII"]

Sl.* No.	No. of replicates	Average growth of fungus (in m m.)		Average % of inhibition	
		At 1000 ppm	At 500 ppm	At 1000 ppm	At 500 ppm
1.	3	18	15	40	50
2.	3	13	12	56	60
3.	3	8	10	73	66
4.	3	10	13	66	56
5.	3	5	10	83	66
6.	3	4	5	86	83
7.	3	2	4	98	86
8.	3	2	3	93	90
9.	3	13	10	56	66
10.	3	15	17	40	43
11.	3	1	5	96	83
12.	3	2	7	93	76
Control		30	30		

* The serial number of compounds correspond to those given in Table 2.

in Table 3. The percentage inhibition was calculated according to Vincent's (1947) formula which is as follows :

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{Ac - At}{Ac} \times 100$$

Ac = Area of the colony in control plate, At = Area of the colony in test plate.

The results indicated that compounds Nos. 7,8, 11,12 show greater inhibition at 1000 ppm. Compounds containing $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{Cl}$ cause greater inhibition in the growth of fungus.

The antiviral activity of four compounds Nos. 1,8 (Table 1), Nos 1,8 (Table 2) have been tested. The protection rate (survival %) and MST (Mean survival time) was calculated by following formulae :

$$\% S = \frac{\text{Survival number of animals}}{\text{Initial number of animals}} \times 100$$

$$\text{MST} = \frac{\text{Summation of time taken for each animal to die} + \text{Summation of Survival time of animal not dying}}{\text{Number of animals dying} + \text{Number of animals surviving}}$$

The results indicated that only one compound 3-[2-(5-chlorobenzylidene)-4-thiazolidinone] diazo]-6-fluoroindol-2-one possess some activity.

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